

A hybrid approach to address the transition to quantum-resistant cryptography in telecommunication environments

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Abstract—The existence of a cryptographically relevant quantum computer threatens the widely used classical cryptosystems such as RSA, DSA, ECDH and ECDSA. In order to communicate securely when those types of quantum computers exist, it is necessary to use quantum-resistant cryptography, which includes quantum and post-quantum cryptography. However, classical cryptography is so embedded in our current technology that the transition to purely quantum-resistant cryptography is a highly complex task. A hybrid approach among classical, quantum and post-quantum cryptography is the safest way to face this challenge. In this paper, we describe our hybrid approach to secure the communications in a telecommunications environment. Concretely, we propose a hybridization module that can be easily integrated in telecommunication architectures. It will provide a symmetric quantum-resistant key to and agent that will establish a quantum-secure IPsec tunnel between endpoints. The security is based on quantum and post-quantum protocols, providing the IPsec tunnel with a double quantum-resistant security shell.

Index Terms—quantum networks, quantum communication, quantum key distribution, post-quantum cryptography.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today’s digital era, secure communications have become paramount in every field, from personal exchanges to critical business transactions. To establish reliable communication, we must ensure three essential security principles: confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. Confidentiality prevents unauthorized access to sensitive information, authentication verifies

the identity of communicating parties, and integrity ensures that data remains unaltered during transmission. Cryptography is the foundational tool that enables us to implement these principles effectively, providing a secure framework to protect information and ensure trustworthiness in our communications. Its core idea is that two parties wishing to communicate securely must possess a shared secret, commonly known as a “secret key”. This shared key enables encryption and decryption, ensuring that only those who know the key can access the information. However, securely sharing this secret key over an untrusted channel is a challenging task. To solve this problem, asymmetric cryptography was introduced, a method that relies on one-way functions. This approach allows each party to generate a public-private key pair: the public key can be openly shared, while the private key remains confidential. The most widely used asymmetric algorithms today include RSA (Rivest–Shamir–Adleman) [1], which is based on the difficulty of factoring large prime numbers, and ECC (Elliptic Curve Cryptography) [2], [3], which leverages the complexity of the algebraic structure of elliptic curves over finite fields. These algorithms enable secure key exchange, allowing the parties to establish a shared secret.

One of the fundamental challenges in computer science is the theoretical proof of the existence of one-way functions, which are mathematical functions that are easy to compute in one direction but difficult to invert without specific information. Currently, we rely on empirical evidence to support the feasibility of public-key cryptography, meaning that its security rests on the assumption that no efficient algorithms to invert these one-way functions exist. This assumption un-

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derpins the security of widely used cryptographic algorithms, such as RSA. So far, these algorithms have remained secure because no classical computational methods have been able to efficiently reverse the underlying one-way functions. However, this security could be compromised by advancements in quantum computing, which, through algorithms like Shor’s algorithm [4], could potentially solve these problems efficiently, posing a unprecedented threat to current cryptographic standards. Shor’s algorithm is capable of efficiently factoring large numbers and solving discrete logarithms, mathematical problems that form the basis of widely used cryptographic algorithms such as RSA and ECC. With a sufficiently powerful quantum computer, these cryptographic systems can be broken, allowing encrypted data to be decrypted with ease. This vulnerability has led to concerns about “harvest now, decrypt later” attacks, in which malicious actors intercept and store data encrypted with quantum-vulnerable cryptosystems, intending to decrypt it later once quantum technology advances. This strategy is particularly concerning for sensitive information that requires long-term confidentiality, as these actors could eventually compromise today’s secure communications once quantum computing becomes viable. As a result, this looming threat underscores the urgent need to develop and transition to quantum-resistant cryptographic algorithms to protect the integrity of modern communications.

To address the threat that quantum computers pose to classical cryptography, two main approaches have been developed: quantum cryptography and post-quantum cryptography. Quantum cryptography relies on the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics to ensure security. This means that its security is theoretically guaranteed, independent of an eavesdropper’s computational power. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), for example, uses these quantum principles to detect any interception attempts, as any measurement by an eavesdropper would inherently disturb the quantum states, alerting the communicating parties to a security breach [5]. Therefore, quantum cryptography is considered unconditional secure [6]. However, it requires specialized hardware that is expensive. QKD systems rely on delicate quantum states for secure key exchange, which demands highly precise equipment, such as single-photon sources and detectors, and often operates only over limited distances or through dedicated fiber-optic lines. On the other hand, post-quantum cryptography aims to adapt classical cryptographic techniques to resist attacks from both quantum and classical computers. It bases its security on mathematical problems that are believed to be resistant to quantum algorithms, such as lattice-based problems, code-based cryptography, and multivariate polynomial equations [7]. However, like classical cryptography, post-quantum cryptography faces the inherent limitation that the existence of true one-way functions has yet to be theoretically proven. This implies that, while these algorithms are believed to be secure against both classical and quantum attacks, there is no absolute guarantee that a classical or quantum algorithm won’t eventually be discovered that could efficiently invert these one-way functions.

The ideal solution to achieving robust quantum-resistant cryptography lies in a hybrid approach that combines QKD, post-quantum cryptography (PQC), and classical cryptography. By using these three methods together, it is possible to generate cryptographic material with up to three layers of security, ensuring that the material remains secure as long as at least one of the underlying keys remains secure. This approach covers a wide range of potential attack scenarios, providing a highly resilient structure against both current and future threats. For example, if an eavesdropper were to intercept the quantum channel used in QKD, the cryptographic material would still be secure, as it would depend on the additional layers provided by PQC and classical cryptography. Similarly, if a breakthrough algorithm were to emerge that could defeat PQC algorithms, the material would remain protected thanks to the strength of QKD and classical encryption methods. This layered strategy ensures that even if one of the security mechanisms is compromised, the remaining secure layers continue to protect the cryptographic material, making it far more resistant to evolving threats in the quantum era.

There are families of cryptographic algorithms that incorporate hybrid cryptographic material to strengthen its security in the way described above. Some examples are the Hybrid Authenticated Key Exchange (HAKE) algorithms, that incorporate classical, quantum and post-quantum material to perform an Authenticated Key Exchange (AKE) using pre-shared keys [8]–[11], or the Muckle+ protocol [12], which is an extension of [11] that replaces the authentication mechanism through pre-shared keys with a post-quantum authentication. Moreover, there is work on the security models for AKE mechanisms with QKD, see [13]. Although those proposals provide a complete hybrid solution for AKE at a theoretical level, this paper focuses on the building blocks that enable the implementation, at a system level, of this family of HAKE algorithms and beyond. Following this idea, we propose a building block for the transition to quantum-resistant cryptography that fits into typical architectures of telecommunications environments. Concretely, we define and describe the workflow of a hybridization module, which is responsible for creating hybrid cryptographic material that will serve to establish an quantum-resistant IPsec tunnel by the agent.

The paper is structured as follows. In section II we review the hybridization methods that will be implemented in the hybridization module. In section III we give a little bit of context about the QUBIP project to motivate the development of the hybridization module, which will be described in section IV. Finally, section V is dedicated to the conclusions and future work.

II. SYMMETRIC KEY HYBRIDIZATION

When n symmetric keys K_1, K_2, \dots, K_n are generated, they can be combined to generate a hybrid¹ symmetric K . The

¹The terms ‘hybrid key’ and ‘combined key’ will be used as a synonyms throughout this paper.

properties of this hybrid key will depend on the method used to perform the hybridization and the properties of the component keys K_1, K_2, \dots, K_n . The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) recommends three different methods to generate a hybrid key from n symmetric component keys [14]. Those are:

- Concatenation:

$$K = K_1 \parallel \dots \parallel K_n$$

- Exclusive-Oring:

$$K = K_1 \oplus \dots \oplus K_n$$

- A key-extraction process:

$$K = T(\text{HMAC-hash}(\text{salt}, K_1 \parallel \dots \parallel K_n \parallel D_1 \parallel \dots \parallel D_m), \text{kLen}) \quad (1)$$

Where $T(x, \text{kLen})$ is the truncation function which truncates the variable x to a length of kLen , HMAC-hash is the HMAC function defined by the corresponding hash function, and the salt and D_1, \dots, D_m variables are optional secret or non-secret bit strings.

Those methods have different relation among quantities such as the key length or min-entropy of the component and hybrid keys [14]. For example, the exclusive-or-ing method requires that at least one of the component keys has equal or greater min-entropy than the min-entropy required for the combined key, while the concatenation method requires that the sum of the min-entropies of the component keys shall be equal or greater than the required min-entropy of the combined key. There are also other features and issues that differentiate the methods from each other. For example, through concatenation we achieve a combined key whose length is the sum of the length of the component keys, while through exclusive-or-ing the component and combined keys will have the same length. However, if one of the component keys is disclosed, part of the combined key obtained through concatenation will be disclosed too, while the combined key obtained through exclusive-or-ing will remain private (as long as the other component keys remain private).

III. TRANSITION TO QUANTUM-RESISTANT CRYPTOGRAPHY: QUBIP PROJECT

The transition from classical cryptography to quantum-resistant cryptography is a highly non-trivial task, since classical cryptosystems are extremely embedded in our current and heterogeneous technology. The change of the cryptographic algorithms impacts a number of functions and protocols in a unknown cascade of dependencies. An effective transition should be done and demonstrated at a system level rather than a building block level. This is where the QUBIP project comes into play. The main objective of QUBIP is to demonstrate the transition from classical cryptography to quantum-resistant cryptography at different levels [15]. This includes the adoption of PQC at a hardware level (for IoT devices), software level (including the transition of widely used cryptographic

libraries such as OpenSSL and NSS, operating systems such as Fedora and applications such as Firefox) and communication protocols level (such as TLS and IPsec). Those PQ (post-quantum) building blocks will be integrated into three pilot demonstrators which will run several use cases to validate the transition at a system level. Those three pilot demonstrators are

- Quantum-secure IoT-based Digital Manufacturing
- Quantum-secure Internet browsing
- Quantum-secure Software Network Environments for Telco Operators

The knowledge gained through the transition exercise of those pilot demonstrators and the results obtained through the use cases will serve to achieve the objective of the QUBIP project, namely, to build a replicable transition process that will serve as a guideline for future transition exercises. Within this context, our contribution focuses on providing hybrid functionalities to the Quantum-secure Software Network Environments for Telco Operators pilot.

IV. HYBRIDIZATION MODULE WITHIN QUANTUM-SECURE SOFTWARE NETWORK ENVIRONMENTS

IPsec tunnels are essential for establishing a secure connection between two points over an IP network, typically across untrusted channels like the Internet. An IPsec tunnel creates a private and encrypted communication pathway, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of data transmitted between endpoints [16]. This protocol suite encapsulates and encrypts IP packets, making it foundational for Virtual Private Networks (VPNs), where it supports secure remote access and site-to-site connections. To establish an IPsec tunnel, cryptographic material is required to encrypt and authenticate the data exchanged between endpoints. Nowadays, the cryptographic material used to establish an IPsec tunnel comes from classical cryptographic algorithms, such as Diffie-Hellman key exchange [17] for generating shared secrets and AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) [18] for data encryption. Authentication is often provided by mechanisms like digital certificates, relying on Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) using RSA or ECDSA algorithms [19]. While these methods are highly secure against classical computing attacks, they are vulnerable to quantum attacks. In our case, this cryptographic material will be derived from a hybrid approach combining QKD and PQC, protecting the IPsec tunnel against classical and quantum attacks. To achieve this, we propose the hybridization module as one of the fundamental building blocks that will enable the establishment of an hybrid IPsec tunnel. This module acts as an interface among the key providers (this is, a QKD device and a PQ protocol) and the agent, which is responsible for establishing the IPsec tunnel. It provides hybrid or non-hybrid symmetric key (depending on the availability) on-demand to the agent.

It is worth it to note that the hybridization module communicates with the agent and the key providers through standardized interfaces, as it will be explained in the next section. Hence, this paper doesn't cover the Internet Key Exchange

(IKE) protocol that is performed by the agent through the controller to establish an IPsec tunnel. The establishment of the hybrid quantum-resistant IPsec tunnel using the key material provided by the hybridization module encompasses different technologies, architectures and workflows that go beyond the scope of this work. This will be addressed in future publications.

A. Architecture and implementation of the hybridization module

The architecture of the hybridization module is depicted in Fig. 1. The workflow is as follows. The agent in Alice, which

Fig. 1. Architecture of the hybridization module for the Alice node. The same architecture applies for Bob.

is responsible for establishing the communication between Alice and Bob, makes a key request through the standard ETSI GS QKD 004 [20] to the hybridization module in Alice. This key request is defined by a key size and a hybridization method. With this information the hybridization module starts two processes. By one side it makes a key request through the standard ETSI GS QKD 004 [20] to the QKD module in Alice. This QKD module provides the quantum generated key between the endpoints Alice and Bob through the quantum channel. By other side, the hybridization module in Alice starts a PQC Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM). It generates a pair of private-public keys through the standardized Module-Lattice-Based Key-Encapsulation Mechanism Standard (ML-KEM) [21]. The private key will be the decapsulation key, while the public key will be the encapsulation key. The encapsulation key is shared with Bob, which uses it to generate the shared secret and a cyphertext that will be sent to Alice. This cyphertext is decapsulated by Alice using the decapsulation key, obtaining the shared secret generated by Bob, which will be the PQ symmetric key. This set of encapsulation and decapsulation algorithms (ML-KEM) are implemented through the open-source library liboqs [22]. Those two processes are finalized when the corresponding symmetric key is delivered to the hybridization module or when a predefined timeout is triggered, whatever happens first. Then, the hybridization module may have four possible scenarios:

- 1) A quantum symmetric key obtained through the QKD module and a PQ symmetric key obtained through ML-KEM.
- 2) A quantum symmetric key obtained through the QKD module.
- 3) A PQ symmetric key obtained through ML-KEM.
- 4) No symmetric key obtained.

In the first scenario, both keys are composed through the method specified by the agent and delivered to the agent through the standard ETSI GS QKD 004 [20]. The result is a hybrid key that, depending on the hybridization method, will remain secure as long as one of the component keys remains secure. In the second and third scenario, the hybridization module will consider that the missing key is a bitstring of zeros with the same length as the key length of the corresponding requested key, and will apply the hybridization method as usual. The result will be a symmetric key that, depending on the hybridization method, may be or not equal to the correctly provided symmetric key (i.e., the quantum key or the PQ key for the second and third cases, respectively). This resulting key won't be a composed key, since only one component key has been used. Lastly, in the fourth scenario, where no keys are provided by the QKD module nor the ML-KEM, the hybridization module will return an error message to the agent.

The hybridization module also manages the key sizes depending on the hybridization method chosen. Although any hybridization method can be implemented, we will consider only the exclusive-oring and the key-extraction process previously described. For the exclusive-oring, the key sizes of the component keys must be equal to the key size of the composed key. In this case, the key size management of the hybridization module is straightforward: it will request quantum and post-quantum key with the same key size as the one requested by the agent, so that the combined key will have the requested key size. For the key-extraction process, the component keys don't have restrictions for the key size, but the composed key, because of the truncation, will have always a key size less than or equal to the key size requested by the agent, which is the parameter $kLen$ in Eq. (1). We can match the key size requested by the agent and the key size delivered by the hybridization module by limiting the allowed requested key size by the agent taking into account the size of the output of the HMAC-hash function, which will depend on the size of the output of the corresponding hash function. In this way, only a request with a key size of at most the size of the output of the hash function will be allowed.

This operating mode of the hybridization module has two important features. First, the maximum level of security is always provided by default, since the module will always request key from the QKD module and the PQC KEM, so the composed key will remain secure as long as the hybridization method and at least one of the component keys remain secure. This level of security is based on the security of QKD and PQC. For the first case, the symmetric key, at a theoretical level, is information-theoretic secure (ITS), which means that it is secure against adversaries with unlimited computational

resources and time. However, the implementation of this technology requires dedicated hardware such as specific devices, and if there is an adversary trying to obtain information about the key, the protocol won't return any cryptographic material. On the other hand, the PQ algorithms necessary to provide the PQ symmetric key (ML-KEM in our case) are easy to implement in a telecommunications network, but its security, at a theoretical level, is not ITS but computationally secure. Moreover, there is no mathematical proof for the computational security of the PQ algorithms. This means that its security is totally empirical, and requires a period of trust to establish its validity. This leads us to the second important feature: flexibility and service continuity. Through the hybridization module working in the operating mode previously described, we assure the creation of cryptographic material for the agent to feed the IPsec tunnel, since the absence of one of the two channels (QKD or PQC KEM) doesn't imply the absence of the key that will be delivered to the agent. This flexibility and service continuity may be an essential requirement to ensure the communication in critical scenarios, together with the high level of security obtained by the hybridization of quantum cryptography and PQC.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we propose and hybrid approach for quantum-resistant telecommunication environments. Concretely, we design and hybridization module which attends the key request of the network agent to provide hybrid symmetric keys, so a quantum-secure IPsec tunnel with two layers of quantum safety can be established between the endpoints. This hybridization module uses the standard ETSI GS QKD 004 to receive key requests from the agent and to request key to the QKD module. Also, it makes use of the standardized PQC KEM, ML-KEM, to establish a PQ symmetric key. Then, the hybridization module combines both keys to obtain a hybrid (or composed) key that will be delivered to the agent. This hybrid key will remain quantum-secure as long as the hybridization method and at least one of the two keys remain secure, providing the IPsec tunnel two features: a high level of security (since the combined key comes from quantum and post-quantum sources) and flexibility (if one of the keys is missing, the IPsec tunnel will still be quantum-secure and the communication can be established).

Future work includes the integration of a classical channel, so a classical symmetric key can be combined together with the quantum and post-quantum keys. Although this layer won't add security against quantum attacks, it will give confidence to implement this hybridization module for a possible scenario in which the noise in the quantum channel is so high that no quantum key can be distilled (because an eavesdropper or bad conditions within the channel), and the PQC KEM is broken by a classical computer (because of the low maturity of this technology).

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